

Deliverable 7.5

Portfolio of Tools and Activities to Promote MARCO-BOLO

Version 1.0

M12 - November 2023

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ERINN Innovation (ERINN)

PUBLIC

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¹ Dissemination level: **PU**: Public⁴

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Executive Summary

Objective

The objective of Deliverable 7.5 (Portfolio of Tools and Activities to promote MARCO-BOLO) is to facilitate MARCO-BOLO’s communication, dissemination, and outreach activities by developing a range of tools and resources to promote and raise awareness of the project and its results amongst stakeholders over the full course of the project.

Rationale

The MARCO-BOLO portfolio of communication, dissemination, and outreach resources will support partners to promote the project, its objectives, and results to a variety of audiences and possible end-users consistently and efficiently.

This deliverable report presents a detailed overview of the communication, dissemination, and outreach resources that have been developed since the start of the project up until M12 (November 2023), and it also gives an overview of the future elements of the portfolio. All resources scheduled to be developed by M12 (project logo, brand guidelines, project website, social media, promotional factsheet, pull-up banner, promotional poster, promotional video, and different communication templates) have been achieved before this due date.

The team(s) involved in deliverable writing:

ERINN Innovation (ERINN)

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1. Introduction

The MARCO-BOLO portfolio of communication, dissemination and outreach resources aims to facilitate the communication and dissemination of the project, its objectives, results, and findings to various stakeholders and possible end-users. It is intended to help partners communicate about the project and its results consistently and efficiently.

Developing the MARCO-BOLO communication, dissemination and outreach tools and resources began with designing a strong project brand which is an important element of the project, as its visual presentation highly influences the recognition and perception of a brand. A brand's visual identity is something that people instantly recognise and associate with the project any time they see it and is subsequently important for project awareness. Effective visual brand identity is achieved by consistently using visual elements to create distinction, such as specific graphic elements, fonts, and colours.

During the first twelve months of the project, the following resources were developed:

- Project logo and accompanying brand guidelines;
- Promotional project factsheet;
- Different templates for a variety of presentation formats (oral presentation, poster presentation and reports);
- Promotional posters;
- Pull-up banner;
- Slide-deck presentation of the project;
- Introductory video of the project;
- General infographic;
- Project website;
- Social media (Twitter - recently renamed to X - and LinkedIn);
- Press release promoting the project's kick-off.

Upon request from partners, promotional materials can be tailored to suit specific events.

Future resources will include interview-based videos, infographics, additional press releases and promotional articles, outreach campaigns to raise citizens' awareness, to be aligned with other events (partners' Open Days, local Science Outreach events, European Researchers' Night) and other supplementary resources as required to promote project events and activities.

All materials and tools will be maintained and updated, as necessary (website and social media continuously), and further resources will be developed throughout the project in line with the project's Description of Action (DoA) as well as in response to project results and partner and stakeholder requirements. Communication, dissemination, and outreach activities through the use of these resources is an ongoing action of the project, which started in M1 – November 2022, and will be continued throughout the project.

2. Project logo

The project logo is an integral part of the brand, as it is included in all the project’s promotional material, both print and online. The final logo was selected through a consortium vote, as decided by the project coordinator, in the kick-off meeting in March 2023, in Paris. The logo with the majority of votes was selected as the final version.

The logo contains elements that are related to the values and goals of MARCO-BOLO (Figure 1). It represents a framework for biodiversity data and data access. The fish, the shrimp and the coral in the radiating circles represent marine biodiversity. The DNA strand and the satellite in the other two radiating circles represent biodiversity data monitoring methods. The need for increased connectivity and a framework for biodiversity data and access is represented by the blue lines connecting all of the circles. The wave at the centre of the logo represents the importance of our oceans and waters.

The one-colour version logos are intended for applications that are restricted in colour, such as fax, memo etc., or any other time it is not possible to use colour printing techniques (Figure 2a; 2b). The full logo suite is available on the MARCO-BOLO Google Drive, [website](#) or can be requested from ERINN (contact: mathilde@erinn.eu). Guidance on the use of the MARCO-BOLO logo can be found in the Brand Guidelines (see Section 3 below).

Figure 1. MARCO-BOLO logo in colour.

Figure 2a. MARCO-BOLO logo in one colour – black.

Figure 2b. MARCO-BOLO logo in one colour – white.

3. Brand Guidelines

The MARCO-BOLO Brand Guidelines (Appendix 1) offer how all MARCO-BOLO partners can achieve the prescribed standards of presentation. The document includes information on the different versions of the project logo (typeface, colour palette, and their correct use), guidelines for using the PowerPoint and Poster presentation templates, and details on the correct EU and UKRI acknowledgement that must be included with all communication and dissemination activities related to the project. The brand guidelines are available on the MARCO-BOLO Google Drive and [website](#).

4. Promotional Factsheet

A promotional factsheet (Appendix 2) was designed to give the general audience an overview of the MARCO-BOLO project. Note that this is the first promotional factsheet which will be updated as necessary as the project progresses.

The factsheet describes the challenge, its main objectives, and expected results and includes each partner's logo. The factsheet is a full-colour double-sided A4 leaflet and is ready for all partners to print (where relevant) and use when engaging with various audiences.

The factsheet is used to raise general awareness of the project. Partners are encouraged to distribute the factsheet through their networks and at relevant events to promote the project. External stakeholders and interested parties can download the factsheet from the [MARCO-BOLO website](#). Partners can also download the PDF and print version of the factsheet from the MARCO-BOLO shared Google Drive or request it from ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu).

Partners can request the factsheet in another language by contacting ERINN and following the protocol outlined in the MARCO-BOLO PDEC (Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Activities, D7.4, section 6.1.3).

5. Communication Templates

5.1 PowerPoint Presentation Template

A MARCO-BOLO PowerPoint Presentation Template has been developed for use at internal and external events when presenting the MARCO-BOLO project and/or its outcomes (Appendix 3). The template includes one cover slide to include the title of the presentation and the presenting partner's contacts, a main body slide, and a closing "Thank you" slide containing relevant contact details. The general template includes the required acknowledgements from all funding sources (EU and UK). This template can be updated if needed throughout the project please contact ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu). Partners can download this template from the [MARCO-BOLO website](#) and from the MARCO-BOLO shared Google Drive.

5.2 Poster Presentation Template

A Poster Presentation Template has been designed and developed for MARCO-BOLO poster presentations (Appendix 4). The poster is designed for printing on A0 paper in full colour. The poster template is available to download from the MARCO-BOLO shared Google Drive. Partners wishing to print posters in other dimensions should contact ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu).

5.3 Deliverable/Report Template

A Word template has been designed and developed for MARCO-BOLO project deliverables, as well as internal and external reports (Appendix 5). The template includes the MARCO-BOLO branding, set up with heading, formatting, font type, size, and colours. This template can be updated if needed throughout the project please contact ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu). The deliverable template is available to download from the MARCO-BOLO shared Google Drive.

6. Promotional Poster

A generic promotional poster (Appendix 6) has been designed and developed at the very start of the project, to present MARCO-BOLO at events and for promoting the project's work to external stakeholders. The poster highlights the "project at a glance" key information such as the programme, type of action, duration, coordinator, consortium, and total budget. It contains general information about the project such as objectives and expected results. It shows the contact details of the project coordinator, manager and communication responsible. The poster is designed for printing on A0 paper in full colour, partners wishing to print a poster in another dimension should contact ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu). The poster is available to download for future events from the MARCO-BOLO shared Google Drive.

7. Pull-up Banner

A project pull-up banner has been designed and developed to be showcased at MARCO-BOLO-related events and partners' institutions (Appendix 7). The pull-up banner shows the logo, related images and funding and contact information. The pull-up banner dimensions are 850 x 2000mm, please print full colour on one side with a pull-up banner mechanism at the base and a vertical stand. It is available for partners to download from the MARCO-BOLO shared Google Drive.

8. Slide-Deck Presentation of the Project

A slide-deck presentation (Appendix 8) has been designed and developed to help partners present MARCO-BOLO during events. The slide-deck highlights the “project at a glance” key information such as the programme, type of action, duration, coordinator, consortium, and total budget. It contains all project participants' logos and describes the challenge, objectives, each of the seven work packages and the expected impacts of MARCO-BOLO. The slide-deck includes one cover slide showing the long title MARine Coastal BiODiversity Long-term Observations and the MARCO-BOLO acronym. Both the cover and closing “Thank you” slides contain the required acknowledgements from all funding sources (EU and UK) as well as the social media channels. It is available to download from the MARCO-BOLO shared Google Drive

9. Project Videos

MARCO-BOLO is developing a professional promotional video (Appendix 9). The video is meant for a broad audience to promote the project and the value of the research being conducted by MARCO-BOLO. Shorter media clips of the promotional video will be used by partners to promote the main elements of the project on social media channels (following relevant Awareness Days). It introduces the challenges facing marine, coastal and freshwater biodiversity, and the possible solutions MARCO-BOLO could provide to enhance biodiversity monitoring, data collection and access to enable science-based decision-making for policies to protect and restore ocean health. The visuals and narrative of the video were developed by ERINN with input from the MARCO-BOLO coordinator EMBRC.

In addition, at least five shorter media clips will be developed throughout the project, based on the main results and activities as they are being developed.

All videos will be published on the [MARCO-BOLO website](#), shared through the MARCO-BOLO [Twitter/X](#), through the [MARCO-BOLO LinkedIn](#), and added to the [ERINN YouTube](#). Partners will be asked to share the video and/or shorter media clips with their wider networks. It is hoped that the video will be adopted by the partnership for use in their existing international outreach activities.

10. Project Explainer Infographic

A project explainer infographic (Appendix 10) has been designed and developed to promote MARCO-BOLO's aims and objectives online. It is published and visible on the [MARCO-BOLO website](#) under the “Project Overview” and “Resources” webpages and can be used by partners to promote and explain MARCO-BOLO throughout the project. The infographic depicts the project's challenges, objectives and aims under three captions: “The Problem”, “MARCO-BOLO Solution” and “The Outcome”.

11. Website

The project website (www.marcobolo-project.eu) is a key tool for promoting the project and disseminating the project's objectives, work plan and results to a wide audience including all stakeholders and possible end-users. The website is fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679, GDPR) by incorporating a Data Policy and Privacy Statement located in the website footer. This informs website visitors about what MARCO-BOLO does with any personal data gathered. Google Analytics is used to track traffic and monitor the use of the website.

To ensure the successful promotion of the project, sustain the interest of the target audience and attract new users, the website's content is maintained and updated with new information throughout the project's lifetime. The website will remain active for five years after the end of the project, to serve as a valuable public resource of research information on the subject and to promote the outputs of publicly funded research in the domain beyond the project's lifetime.

The website's key features are:

- A main **"Home Page"** with a general overview of the project, including the main categories of the web page with direct links to the latest news and events. The top menu bar contains buttons for sections of the website on **"About"**, **"Community of Practice"**, **"News"**, **"Events"**, **"Results"**, **"Resources"**, **"Related Projects"** and other useful links to the project's X/Twitter and LinkedIn. The home page also has a search bar to quickly navigate the website and a **"Subscribe for news"** link, where the public can subscribe to MARCO-BOLO's stakeholder database mailing list. This database will be used to send registered stakeholders the latest news about the project and engage more directly.

Figure 3. Main **"Homepage"** of MARCO-BOLO website.

Sign up to MARCO-BOLO news for updates on our events, results and progress.

By signing up, you acknowledge that you're aware your personal data will be used in line with our [Privacy Statement](#), MARCO-BOLO do not share the information provided on this form with other outside parties. You can change your mind at any time by clicking the unsubscribe link in the footer of any email you receive from us.

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101082021 (MARCO-BOLO). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. UK participants in MARCO-BOLO are supported by the UKRI's Horizon Europe Guarantee under the Grant No. XXXXXXXXX (MS); No. 10063994 (MBA) and No. 10048178 (NOC).

Email Address

First Name

Figure 4. “Subscribe for news” form.

- An “**About**” tab which leads to three pages:
 - A general “**Project Overview**” page, indicating the challenge, the main objectives and expected results of the project.
 - A “**Project Team**” page, where the full Consortium is listed with easy-to-read logos and names. Users can access more detailed information about each listed partner (including their role in the project, contact information and official website) by clicking on the “view partner” link.
 - A “**Work Packages**” page, where all 7 work packages are listed. Users can access more detailed information about each work package (the objectives, lead partner and contacts) by clicking on the work package associated image.
- A “**Community of Practice**” tab which leads to five pages:
 - A “**Community of Practice**” page, which defines and explains the MARCO-BOLO Community of Practice (CoP). The page mentions the MARCO-BOLO CoP objectives, aims, and planned future workshops.
 - A “**Membership**” page, where users can find the “who, how and why” type of information on joining the MARCO-BOLO CoP.
 - A “**Survey**” page, where users could find information and links to the MARCO-BOLO Biodiversity Survey which ran from July to October 2023.
 - A “**Co-Design and Co-Creation**” yet empty page, which will contain information on measures that have been taken to help co-design and co-create biodiversity data products by and for users.
 - A “**Contact**” page, leading users to the main contact of the MARCO-BOLO CoP.

- A “News” and an “Events” tab show project news, notices, press releases, events, and updates from MARCO-BOLO and associated projects. This category is regularly updated with events organized by the MARCO-BOLO consortium, as well as events where MARCO-BOLO partners are represented. This category also includes any other events of interest to the partnership such as conferences or workshops.

Figure 5. “News” web page.

Figure 6. “Events” web page.

- A “**Results**” tab is used as a platform and repository for public deliverables and outputs (data, reports, and publications). It will list project deliverables and innovation outputs as soon as they become available. This section includes a continuously updated “**Publications**” tab which lists open-access scientific publications and articles. Partners are expected to publish their results in high-impact, Open-Access, peer-reviewed journals, and publish review articles and editorials where possible.

Figure 7. “Results” web page.

- The “**Resources**” menu provides direct access to the print, audio, and video media that will be created throughout the whole lifecycle of the project. It houses communication and dissemination tools and resources such as videos, press releases and project factsheets.

Figure 8. “Resources” web page.

- A “**Related Projects**” tab documents the other projects funded under the Call ‘HORIZON-CL6-2022-BIODIV-01-01’ as well as other similar initiatives associated with MARCO-BOLO. Clicking on each project's logo takes the user to a dedicated page with more detailed information and the related project’s website link.

Figure 9. “Related Projects” web page.

- Website footer contains the acknowledgements of the funding sources and ensures they are always visible. The “**Contact Us**” area gives the project coordinator, the project management, and the project communications emails. This area also links to the official X/Twitter and LinkedIn of MARCO-BOLO and the contact email info@marcobolo-project.eu, which redirects emails to ERINN. The Data Policy and Privacy statements are also found within the footer.

12. Social Media

Social networking is part of the MARCO-BOLO communication strategy. A dedicated project Twitter/X account (@MARCOBOLO_EU) and LinkedIn account (MARCO-BOLO) were set up at the start of the project and are used to post MARCO-BOLO relevant information. The X and LinkedIn pages are maintained by ERINN and project-related tweets are posted regularly. Targeted promotional campaigns will be carried out to promote specific topics where relevant. Depending on social media developments, other social media channels may be considered in the future.

Figure 10. Twitter/X (left, 285 followers) and LinkedIn (right, 101 followers) MARCO-BOLO accounts.

13. Press Releases

The first press release, to announce the launch of MARCO-BOLO, was published on 7 December 2022 (Appendix 11). The press release was uploaded to Alpha Galileo (an independent business-to-business science news service for the research and media communities) and distributed to partners with the request to distribute widely through their networks (approved GDPR stakeholder mailing lists and related project networks). It was also uploaded to the project website under the “News” and “Resources” sections, the MARCO-BOLO X/Twitter account and shared on the ERINN LinkedIn and X accounts.

The first press release introducing the project was effectively disseminated through the following partners and related projects’ websites and social media channels:

- **EMBRIC:** <https://www.embric.eu/newsroom/news/marco-bolo-start>
- **ERINN:** <https://erinn.eu/eu-project-launched-to-better-understand-marine-biodiversity-decline-and-restore-ocean-health/>
- **MBA:** <https://www.countryside-jobs.com/article/2022-12-13-eu-project-marco-bolo-launched-to-better-understand-marine-biodiversity-decline-and-restore-ocean-health>
& https://www.linkedin.com/posts/marine-biological-association_eu-project-marco-bolo-launched-to-better-activity-7008049375583027200-rRwp/?originalSubdomain=ir
- **EU4OceanObs:** <https://www.eu4oceanobs.eu/marco-bolo-observations-marine-biodiversity-decline-and-restore-ocean-health/>
- **Fish Focus:** <https://fishfocus.co.uk/new-eu-marine-biodiversity-project/>

14. Collaboration With Other Projects and Initiatives

MARCO-BOLO aims to actively cooperate with the other projects selected under the same funding call (Biodiversity and ecosystem services (HORIZON-CL6-2022-BIODIV-01): OBAMA-NEXT and DiverSea) and complementary successful projects where possible. Collaboration is key in EU-funded projects, where possibilities emerge thanks to knowledge transfer, networking, and direct interaction with policymakers. This is the reason why we keep the “[Related Projects](#)” tab on our website up-to-date and stay informed on their progress, as well as share our news with them. The representatives from these related projects (OBAMA-NEXT, BIOcean5D, Biodiversa+, EuropaBON, EU4OceanOBS, MBON and DTO-BioFlow) each attended the MARCO-BOLO kick-off meeting and had an allocated time to introduce their projects.

Tuesday, March 14th

Videoconference link: <https://us06web.zoom.us/j/83640987773?pwd=Vm1oUVAYTkN2TWZSdnE0dmVjcHFhMUT09>

Phone connection: please contact davide.dicioccio@embrc.eu for a specific country phone no.

Plenary session		<i>Room 109, Tower 44-55, 1st floor</i>
9:00	Introduction	Nicolas Pade, project coordinator
9:10	Greetings from the Project Officer & European Commission Expectations	Laura Palomo Rios, EC Project Officer
9:15	European Policy Context and Opportunities for MARCO-BOLO	Zoi Konstantinou (DG MARE) Alice Belin (DG ENV) Eduardo Carqueijeiro (DG RTD)
9:45	The OBAMA-NEXT project	Jacob Carstensen, OBAMA-NEXT coordinator
10:05	The BioOcean5D project	Josipa Bilic Zimmermann, BioOcean5D scientific coordinator
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee break	<i>Room 102, Tower 44-55, 1st floor</i>
11:00	The Biodiversa+ project	Michelle Silva Del Pozo and Guillaume Body, Biodiversa+
11:20	The EuropaBON project	Maria Lumbierres, EuropaBON
11:40	EU4OceanOBS	Maria Grigoratou, EU4OceanOBS coordinator
12:00	The DTO Bioflow project	Klaas Deneudt, DTO Bioflow coordinator
12:20	The Marine Biodiversity Observation Network (MBON)	Frank Muller-Kager, MBON co-chair
12:40 – 14:00	Lunch	<i>Room 102, Tower 44-55, 1st floor</i>

Figure 11. Part of MARCO-BOLO Kick-Off meeting agenda.

During the afternoon, a special session took place where coordinators from various projects engaged in discussions with MARCO-BOLO partners to explore optimal collaboration methods and identify specific activities. Several initiatives were considered, including the potential formation of working groups comprising representatives from different projects, such as those focused on communication and eDNA.

So far, MARCO-BOLO has actively cooperated with the following projects and initiatives:

- **OBAMA-NEXT EU project 101081642:** MARCO-BOLO cooperates actively with its sister project OBAMA-NEXT. OBAMA-NEXT's goal is to develop a toolbox for generating accurate, precise and relevant information characterising marine ecosystems and their biodiversity. The MARCO-BOLO communication partner ERINN also had a meeting with the OBAMA-NEXT communication partner Science Crunchers in February 2023, where they suggested and discussed how the projects could collaborate on communication and dissemination activities such as social media, policy briefs, joint events etc. UNESCO-IOC, which is tasked with establishing a Community of Practice (CoP) for MARCO-BOLO, organized a call in June 2023 with colleagues of OBAMA-NEXT responsible for stakeholder engagement. They discussed ways in which the two projects can align and support each other to maximize project activities and interaction with stakeholders. A follow-up call was then organized in July 2023 so that UNVIE could provide an overview of the project stakeholder profiling survey. OBAMA-NEXT shared with MARCO-BOLO a list of their anticipated products to see what tools and products can overlap between the two sister projects. MARCO-BOLO and OBAMA-NEXT plan to have a joint General Assembly in the Netherlands in February 2024.
- **The BioEco Panel of the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS)** met with the MARCO-BOLO consortium on 18 September 2023. MARCO-BOLO is meant to contribute to and help implement GOOS BioEco work, in particular, advancing the development of EOVs and EBVs and helping ensure that project outputs and information feed into global processes. The two parties agreed on a Joint Action Plan that aims to serve as a living document and identify areas of potential future collaboration.
- **EuropaBON EU project 101003553:** There have been interactions between MARCO-BOLO and EuropaBON which has been tasked with the development of a potential framework for a European Biodiversity Monitoring Coordination Centre (BMCC). The lack of marine expertise or representation in the EuropaBON project has prompted the consortium to interact with MARCO-BOLO through our data standardisation work, focusing on developing data for EOVs, EBVs, MSFD and WFD indicators. Several MARCO-BOLO colleagues were invited by EuropaBON to participate in a co-design workshop for the European Biodiversity Monitoring Centre (BMCC) held in Leipzig, Germany, in November 2023. The overall aim of the workshop was to gather final input and discuss opportunities and challenges associated with the remaining key deliverables for the project. MARCO-BOLO colleagues had the opportunity to engage and build relationships with consortium members and explore where the marine biodiversity observation community could contribute to this process. MARCO-BOLO's Community of Practice (CoP) has also been a line of communication as a representative of EuropaBON serves as a core member of the CoP which is tasked with providing advice and steering overall stakeholder engagement.
- **Biodiversa+ EU project 101052342:** This project brings together environment agencies and funding agencies from across Europe to work together on funding biodiversity research and monitoring. It is an important link for MARCO-BOLO to ensure engagement with environmental agencies. Biodiversa+ participated in the kick-off meeting of MARCO-BOLO and a representative of Biodiversa+ is serving as a core member of the MARCO-BOLO CoP ensuring their input to MARCO-BOLO deliverable and service development. Interactions have also taken place regarding the Biodiversa+ demonstrator EURockfish, to see how the MARCO-BOLO partners can support the project.

- **DTO-BioFlow EU project 101112823:** This project aims to bring biological data into the digital twin of the ocean initiative. MARCO-BOLO is working together with DTO-BioFlow to uncover long-term time series for the northeast Atlantic for the analysis of biodiversity trends. The projects launched a joint call for data. The two projects are also now exploring whether there is any potential to link up via the MARCO-BOLO CoP regarding the 1st MARCO-BOLO Co-Design Workshop to be held in early 2024.
- **BiOceans5D EU project 101059915:** BIOcean5D is a major interdisciplinary project designed to better understand the impact of human activity on Europe's seas and coastlines. MARCO-BOLO is working with BIOcean5D on the implementation of data standards, with BIOceans5D using extensive parts of the MARCO-BOLO data management plan (DMP) as well as suggesting improvements that will be adopted in WP1's update of the DMP.
- **MARCO-BOLO partner CIIMAR (Task 7.4 Lead):** Hosted a session titled "Improving Cooperation between European Projects" during the European Marine Biology Symposium (2-8 September 2023). Coordinators showcased five EU projects and initiatives (ACTNOW, MarinePlan, MPA Europe, MBON Europe, iAtlantic) and explored strategies for enhancing collaboration during ongoing research projects. The discussion extended to effective cooperation in engaging with policymakers and society. Following a fruitful audience discussion, it was agreed to organize dedicated sessions on project cooperation in future EMBS meetings.

Appendix

Appendix 1. Brand Guidelines

MARCO-BOLO
Brand Guidelines

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3 MARCO-BOLO Brand Guidelines

INTRODUCTION

Brand guidelines

The brand guidelines set out in this manual for **MARCO-BOLO** offer the means by which all **MARCO-BOLO** partners can achieve the prescribed standards of presentation related to the **MARCO-BOLO** project.

It is recommended that partners follow the standards given in this manual to ensure a high standard of project presentation in all **MARCO-BOLO** dissemination activities.

For any queries regarding the implementation of the **MARCO-BOLO** brand guidelines, please contact Avril Hanbidge, (avril@erinn.eu).

marcobolo-project.eu

4 MARCO-BOLO
Brand Guidelines

LOGO

5 MARCO-BOLO Brand Guidelines

LOGO

The **MARCO-BOLO** logo is constructed using a combination of upper case bold lettering and a specially hand crafted accompanying icon.

This section gives you guidelines on how to use the logo in any format, for example the recommended type face to use, the colour palette and best use of the logo on different backgrounds.

Colour Logo

6 MARCO-BOLO
Brand Guidelines

ONE COLOUR LOGO

The one colour version logos are intended for applications that are restricted in colour, such as fax, memo etc. or any time it is not possible to use colour printing techniques.

Black logo

White logo

7 MARCO-BOLO Brand Guidelines

CORRECT USE OF LOGO

Colour background variations

The preferred background for the **MARCO-BOLO** logo is white, but there will be some instances where the logo needs to be used over a colour other than white. In this case, you may have to use either the white or black version of the logo.

Whether the logo is being used in full colour, black or white, please ensure that the logo is always legible and there is sufficient contrast between all the elements; particularly when using the logo with the tagline to ensure the text is legible.

Correct
The full colour logo is only fully visible on a light background.

Incorrect
The full colour logo is not fully visible on a background similar in colour to the logo itself.

Correct
The white logo is only fully visible on a dark background.

Incorrect
The black logo is not fully visible on a dark background.

Correct
The black logo is only fully visible on a light background.

Incorrect
The white logo is not fully visible here on a light background.

8 MARCO-BOLO
Brand Guidelines

CORRECT USE OF LOGO (CTD.)

Photographic background variations

The preferred background for the **MARCO-BOLO** logo is white, but in some cases it is necessary to use the logo over images. In all cases, it is important to ensure that all elements of the logo are clearly visible.

Correct
The full colour logo is fully visible on a light image.

Incorrect
The full colour logo is not fully visible on an image similar in colour to the logo.

Correct
The white logo is fully visible on a dark image.

Incorrect
The black logo is not fully visible on a dark image.

Correct
The black logo is fully visible on a light image.

Incorrect
The white logo is not fully visible on a light image.

9 MARCO-BOLO
Brand Guidelines

CORRECT USE OF LOGO (CTD.)

Clearance space

Clearance space is the area surrounding the logo that should be kept free of other graphical elements. You should allow sufficient space around the logo.

The minimum required space to use around the logo is the height of the "M" of "MARCO-BOLO" from the logotype.

Clearance space for logo

10 MARCO-BOLO Brand Guidelines

CORRECT USE OF LOGO (CTD.)

Minimum size

The **MARCO-BOLO** logo can be increased to any size you require however the minimum size the logo should be displayed at only at 70mm in width. Where possible, the logo should not be used below these sizes as legibility will be compromised.

Minimum size
= 70mm width

11 MARCO-BOLO Brand Guidelines

INCORRECT USE OF LOGO

What not to do

Never recreate elements of the artwork. Do not modify elements or alter colours. Please adhere to the guidelines below.

✘ Do not distort logo

✘ Do not modify colours

✘ Do not rearrange elements

✘ Do not add elements

✘ Do not distort the icon

✘ Do not modify proportion

12 MARCO-BOLO Brand Guidelines

TYPEFACES

Primary – Poppins (Graphic Design Use Only)

Poppins is the primary **MARCO-BOLO** typeface. This simple, modern font helps communicate ideas clearly and confidently. It is highly legible in both print and digital communications. It is available in a range of weights: from light to bold.

Poppins is primarily used for print design.

Poppins Light
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 @*?!&%+="

Poppins Extra Bold
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 @*?!&%+="

Secondary – Calibri (General Use)

Calibri is the secondary **MARCO-BOLO** typeface. **Calibri** reflects the clean look of the primary typeface and should be used whenever possible within Microsoft Office applications i.e. Word, Powerpoint, Excel etc.

Calibri Regular can be used for all standard communication materials e.g. letters/faxes/reports/emails etc.

Calibri is packaged with all Microsoft and Macintosh computers.

Calibri Regular
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 @*?!&%+="

Calibri Bold
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 @*?!&%+="

13 MARCO-BOLO Brand Guidelines

COLOUR PALETTE

Print

The CMYK values are required when preparing materials for professional print jobs.

In-office printing will provide varied results depending on equipment and as a result, 100% colour accuracy cannot be expected.

Web

The RGB values are required when preparing materials for the web.

It is important to note that the calibration of monitors, desktop printers and projection equipment can vary. Please adhere to the RGB values provided to ensure consistency across all materials for the web.

CMYK: 84/58/1/0
RGB: 50/108/179
HEX: 326cb3

CMYK: 70/14/0/0
RGB: 36/171/226
HEX: 24abe2

CMYK: 64/54/56/31
RGB: 85/87/85
HEX: 555755

CMYK: 61/5/50/0
RGB: 100/185/153
HEX: 64b999

14 MARCO-BOLO
Brand Guidelines

APPLICATION

15 MARCO-BOLO Brand Guidelines

POWERPOINT PRESENTATION

Cover, context & closing slides

Please follow the PowerPoint template where possible. The recommended font is Calibri.

Title slide layout

Content slide layouts

We suggest using 24pt for the body font size and at least 40pt for headings.

Closing slide layout

16 MARCO-BOLO Brand Guidelines

POWERPOINT POSTER

Please follow the PowerPoint template where possible. It is A0 in size.
The recommended font is Calibri. There are 2 colour options for the posters.

Poster background layouts

17 MARCO-BOLO Brand Guidelines

WORD TEMPLATE

For project deliverables

Please follow the Word template for project deliverables and reports.
The recommended font is Calibri.

Deliverable X.X
Title of document
Version

Author
Date
Date of update

MARCO-BOLO

Report Title

- Objective**
Write the main objective(s) of this report.
 - 1.1 Sub-heading**
Use when applicable.
 - 1.1.1 Second sub-heading**
Use when applicable.
- Background**
Use when applicable.
- Methodology**
Use when applicable.
- Results and Discussion**

MARCO-BOLO

Report Title

Document Information

Document Name	
Author	
Project Title	
Document Number	
Version	
Project Manager	
Project Lead	
Project Sponsor	
Project Start	
Project End	
Project Status	
Project Phase	
Project Budget	
Project Risk	
Project Impact	
Project Location	
Project Contact	
Project Description	
Project Objectives	
Project Deliverables	
Project Milestones	
Project Risks	
Project Issues	
Project Recommendations	
Project Next Steps	

18 MARCO-BOLO Brand Guidelines

Acknowledgement of EU funding

All publications or any other dissemination relating to results should include the EU emblem and the UKRI logo, together with the following statement to indicate that said results were generated with the assistance of financial support from the EU and UKRI:

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UK participants in MARCO-BOLO are supported by the UKRI's Horizon Europe Guarantee under the Grant No. 10068180 (MS); No. 10063994 (MBA) and No. 10048178 (NOC).

Appendix 2. Promotional Factsheet

marcobolo-project.eu
info@marcobolo-project.eu
X@MARCOCOBOLO_EU
in MARCO-BOLO

MARCO-BOLO (MARine Coastal BIodiversity Long-term Observations) will strengthen European marine, coastal and freshwater biodiversity observation to support decision making, to understand and restore ocean health.

THE CHALLENGE

Coastal and marine areas are incredibly dynamic and productive regions, providing resources and services for both wildlife and people. They are subject to intense pressures from agricultural and industrial pollution primarily through waterways, dredging and building development. National and regional programmes which assess environmental health and human impact on our coasts are often fragmented, short term and uncoordinated at larger scales. **MARCO-BOLO** aims to deliver a transformative change in how marine, coastal and freshwater biodiversity is monitored and managed. Researchers will tailor research and observation data for direct use, delivering practical tools that will allow politicians and companies to determine biodiversity health, predict and monitor changes from imposed policies, and proactively manage environments.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

MARCO-BOLO will enable a digital framework for biodiversity data streams and data access, building on international standards and approaches to establish the biological component of the coastal, marine and freshwater Earth observation infrastructure in Europe. Specific objectives include:

- Improve acquisition, coordination and delivery of marine, coastal and freshwater biodiversity observations to relevant users.
- Enable technologies for cost-effective, timely and accurate biodiversity observations.
- Test new tools, technologies and models to better understand biodiversity decline.
- Empower European biodiversity observatory operators, data producers and users by creating and sharing best practice guidelines for gathering and using biodiversity data to contribute to biodiversity restoration efforts.

AT A GLANCE

PROGRAMME: HORIZON EUROPE (HORIZON-CL6-2022-BIODIV-01-01)

TYPE OF ACTION: Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

DURATION: December 2022 – November 2026 (48 months)

COORDINATOR: European Marine Biological Resource Centre – European Research Infrastructure Consortium (EMBRC-ERIC), France

CONSORTIUM: 28 participants from 14 countries

TOTAL BUDGET: €7.3 million

EXPECTED RESULTS

- **Provide new tools and models:** EVs based on eDNA, real time biodiversity monitoring methods, causal relationships and indicators between external forcings and biological responses.
- **Test of co-designed data streams and workflows:** Validate data exchange across EU and global biodiversity infrastructures, workflows for supporting WFD and MSFD monitoring and map blue carbon benefits and risks of non-indigenous invasive species.
- **Create a European Community of Practice:** Agreed, scalable and transferable pilots and demonstrators producing high quality data streams and support the definition of new governance models for EU biodiversity observations.

CONSORTIUM

The **MARCO-BOLO** consortium brings together 28 organisations from research, industry, government and the not-for-profit sectors across Europe.

CONTACT US:

Project Coordinator:
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Project Manager:
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@MARCBOLO_EU
MARCO-BOLO

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UK Research and Innovation

UK participation in MARCO-BOLO is supported by the UKRI's Horizon Europe Programme under the Grant No. 10048932 (UK) / No. 10048934 (UK) and No. 10048937 (UK).

Appendix 3. PowerPoint Presentation Template

Presentation Title
Event details (title of event, location, date)
Presenter (name and affiliation)

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 ER participants in MARCO-BOLO are supported by the Horizon Europe Guarantee under the Grant No. 101019321 (MOL) No. 101019321 (MOL) No. 101019321 (MOL) No. 101019321 (MOL)

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[MARCO-BOLO](#)
[MarcoBolo-project.eu](#)

Thank you
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Project Manager:
 Claire Laguionie | claire.laguionie@embrc.eu
Communications and Press:
 Mathilde Vidal | mathilde@erinn.eu

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Appendix 4. Poster Presentation Template

Insert Header

Subheading

Body Text

Insert Header

Subheading

Body Text

 MarcoBolo-Project.eu

 @MARCBOLO_EU

 MARCO-BOLO

Project Coordinator:
Nicolas Pade
nicolas.pade@embrc.eu

Press & Communication:
Mathilde Vidal
mathilde@erinn.eu

Funded by the European Union

UK Research and Innovation

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UK participants in MARCO-BOLO are supported by the UKRI Horizon Europe Scheme under the Grant No. 10061313. UKRI, 2023-2025. 10061313 and No. 10061313-0012.

Appendix 5. Deliverable/Report Template

Appendix 6. Promotional Poster

MARCO-BOLO

STRENGTHENING BIODIVERSITY OBSERVATION IN SUPPORT OF DECISION MAKING

marcobolo-project.eu

 @MARCOCOBOLO_EU

 MARCO-BOLO

OBJECTIVES

- Enhance collection, coordination and delivery of marine, coastal and freshwater biodiversity observations for users.
- Develop cost-effective and accurate observation technologies.
- Test and advance new tools, technologies and models.
- Equip European biodiversity data producers and users with best practice guidelines for data-driven restoration.

AT A GLANCE

PROGRAMME: HORIZON EUROPE

TYPE OF ACTION: Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

DURATION: December 2022 – November 2026 (48 months)

COORDINATOR: EMBRC-ERIC, France

CONSORTIUM: 28 participants from 14 countries

TOTAL BUDGET: €7.3 million

EXPECTED RESULTS.

Deliver new tools and models for biodiversity monitoring

Unify and validate data exchange workflows

Establish a Community of Practice with engaged stakeholders

CONTACT US:

<p>Project Coordinator Nicolas Pade EMBRC nicolas.pade@embrc.eu</p>	<p>Project Manager Davide Di Cioccio EMBRC davide.dicioccio@embrc.eu</p>	<p>Press & Communications Mathilde Vidal ERINN mathilde@erinn.eu</p>
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Designed and developed by ERINN

Appendix 7. Pull-up Banner

 MARCO-BOLO

**MARine Coastal BiODiversity
Long-term Observations**

CONTACT US:

Project Coordinator Nicolas Pade EMBRC nicolas.pade@embrc.eu	Project Manager Davide Di Cioccio EMBRC davide.dicioccio@embrc.eu	Press & Communications Mathilde Vidal ERINN mathilde@erinn.eu
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info@marcobolo-project.eu | [@MARCOBOLO_EU](https://twitter.com/MARCOBOLO_EU)
marcobolo-project.eu | [in MARCO-BOLO](https://www.linkedin.com/company/marcobolo)

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Appendix 8. Slide-Deck Presentation

MARCO-BOLO
STRENGTHENING BIODIVERSITY OBSERVATION IN SUPPORT OF DECISION MAKING

MARCO-BOLO
MARine Coastal BiODiversity Long-term Observations

Project Introduction

Presenter (name and affiliation)

@MARCOBOLO_EU MARCO-BOLO MarcoBolo-project.eu

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LE participants in MARCO-BOLO are supported by the Horizon Europe Research under the Grant No. 101019111 (MARCO-BOLO) and the 101019111 (MARCO-BOLO).

AT A GLANCE

PROGRAMME:	Horizon Europe
CALL TOPIC:	HORIZON-CL6-2022-BIODIV-01-01
TYPE OF ACTION:	Research & Innovation Action (RIA)
DURATION:	December 2022 – November 2026 (48 months)
COORDINATOR:	European Marine Biological Resource Centre - European Research Infrastructure Consortium (EMBRC-ERIC), France
CONSORTIUM:	28 participants from 14 countries
TOTAL BUDGET:	€7.3 million

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PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

The MARCO-BOLO consortium brings together 28 organisations from research, industry, government and the not-for-profit sectors across Europe.

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THE CHALLENGE

Coastal and marine areas, vital for wildlife and people, face intense pollution from agriculture, industry, and development. Regional programmes assessing their health are fragmented and short-term.

MARCO-BOLO aims to change how marine, coastal and freshwater biodiversity is monitored and managed.

Adapting research and observation data for politicians and companies to better:

- Determine biodiversity health
- Monitor the impact of decisions and policies on biodiversity and environmental health
- Proactively manage coastal environments

[X@MARC0B0LO_EU](#) [in MARCO-BOLO](#) [weibo MarcoBolo-project.eu](#)

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

MARCO-BOLO is building a framework for European coastal, marine, and freshwater biodiversity data streams and access, to align with global standards.

Key objectives:

- Enhance collection, coordination and delivery of marine, coastal and freshwater biodiversity observations for users.
- Develop cost-effective and accurate observation technologies.
- Test and advance new tools, technologies and models.
- Empower European biodiversity data producers and users with best practice guidelines for data-driven restoration.

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WORK PACKAGES (1-7)

WP1: Delivering Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs): Local to Global Biodiversity (meta)Data for Coastal and Marine Systems

✓ Implement a streamlined FAIR-aligned data management system for complete and high-quality data, ensuring easy online access.

✓ Collaborate with relevant stakeholders to establish digital exchange specifications, for sharing project outputs:

- Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) - with the GOOS Biology and Ecosystems (BioEco) Panel
- Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) - with GEO BON's data management teams
- European environmental monitoring agencies - via the European Environment Agency (EEA) and/or National Focal Points (NFPs) and/or Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) / Water Framework Directive (WFD)

Lead partner:
AWI

Contact:

Pier Luigi Buttigieg (AWI) | pier.buttigieg@awi.de

Dan Lear (MBA) | dble@MBA.ac.uk

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WORK PACKAGES (1-7)

WP2: Validating the Use of Environmental DNA (eDNA)

- ✓ Validate eDNA approaches through extensive meta-analysis and comparisons with traditional methods across EU sites.
- ✓ Develop SOPs for eDNA across various ecosystems and taxonomic groups to align with biodiversity networks' needs.
- ✓ Tuning and integration of available resources necessary for eDNA-based biomonitoring.
- ✓ Derive eDNA-based measures/variables in line with the Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBV), Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and Water Framework Directive (WFD).

Lead partner:

CNRS

Contact:
Chris Bowler (CNRS) | cbowler@biologie.ens.fr

Daniel Morais (UIT) | daniel.morais@uit.no

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WORK PACKAGES (1-7)

WP3: Linking Land and Sea Biodiversity Observation

- ✓ Meta-analyse land and sea biodiversity monitoring in hotspots to meet science and policy needs.
- ✓ Combine and simplify results for broader European use.
- ✓ Identify connections and impacts on coastal biodiversity, by validating workflows in four land-river-sea systems:
 - Danube
 - Elbe
 - Guadalquivir
 - Po

Lead partner:

SGN

Contact:
Peter Haase (SGN) | petechaase@senckenberg.de

Tina Sanders (HEREON) | tina.sanders@hereon.de

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WORK PACKAGES (1-7)

WP4: Mapping Biodiversity with Autonomous Systems

- ✓ Create autonomous systems for georeferenced biodiversity maps (including genomic, taxonomic and habitat characteristics).
- ✓ Establish a cost-effective network of biodiversity sensors in coastal and marine areas.
- ✓ Develop a neural network for remote sensing data to deliver Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) and plankton-driver causal relationships.

Lead partner:

NOC

Contact:
Julie Robidart (NOC) | j.robidart@noc.ac.uk

Patrizio Mariani (DTU) | pat@aquas.dtu.dk

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WORK PACKAGES (1-7)

WP5: Modelling and Mapping Coastal and Marine Biodiversity

- ✓ Demonstrate new knowledge in biodiversity trends through innovative tools and models.
- ✓ Enhance biological indicators and blue carbon mapping with advanced observation approaches and technologies.
- ✓ Provide evidence-based insights for the management of non-indigenous invasive species.
- ✓ Deliver virtual research environments (VRE) and integrated workflows for reproducibility and transparency in data analysis.

Lead partner:

VLIZ

Contact:

Klaas Deneudt (VLIZ) | klaas.deneudt@vliz.be

Cristina Huertas Olivares (Lifewatch-ERIC) | cristina.huertas@lifewatch.eu

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WORK PACKAGES (1-7)

WP6: Stakeholder Engagement and Community Integration

- ✓ Create and mobilise a Community of Practice (CoP) for marine biodiversity stakeholders to optimise knowledge generation, transfer and uptake.
- ✓ Engage stakeholders in co-designing user-friendly data and products that meet their needs.
- ✓ Monitor MARCO-BOLO's progress and impact on improving marine data delivery and uptake.

Lead partner:

SSBE

Contact:

Vicente Fernandez (SSBE) | vicente.fernandez@seascapebelgium.be

Ward Appeltans (UNESCO) | w.appeltans@unesco.org

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WORK PACKAGES (1-7)

WP7: Project Management, Linkages and Communication

- ✓ Effectively communicate MARCO-BOLO's goals, achievements, and results to engage and raise awareness.
- ✓ Ensure sustainability and legacy in all aspects of the project.
- ✓ Educate European citizens on marine biodiversity importance.
- ✓ Engage and collaborate with related EU projects and initiatives to enhance and strengthen outcomes.

Lead partner:

EMBR-ERIC

Contact:

Nicolas Pade (EMBR-ERIC) | nicolas.pade@embrc.eu (Coordination)

Claire Laguionie (EMBR-ERIC) | claire.laguionie@embrc.eu (Management)

Mathilde Vidal (ERINN) | mathilde@erinn.eu (Communications)

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EXPECTED IMPACTS

- ✓ **Provide new tools and models:** Essential Variables (EVs) based on Environmental DNA (eDNA), real-time biodiversity monitoring, causal relationships, and indicators for environmental responses.
- ✓ **Test of co-designed data streams and workflows:** Ensure seamless data exchange in EU and global biodiversity infrastructures, support Water Framework Directive (WFD) and Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) monitoring and assess blue carbon impacts and non-indigenous invasive species risks.
- ✓ **Create a Community of Practice (CoP):** Create scalable, high-quality data streams, and coordinate EU biodiversity observations in alignment with international standards and best practices.

[@MARC0B0LD_EU](#) [MARC0-B0LD](#) [MarcoBolo-project.eu](#)

Thank you
Presenter contact details

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Project Manager:
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 EMBRC participants in MARCO-B0LD are supported by the EMER, Horizon Europe Executive under the Grant No. 101000011 (MARC0-B0LD) and No. 101011111 (EMER).

Appendix 9. Project Video (screenshots)

D7.5 Portfolio of Tools and Activities to Promote MARCO-BOLO

MARCO-BOLO
STRENGTHENING BIODIVERSITY OBSERVATION IN SUPPORT OF DECISION MAKING

THE MARCO-BOLO CONSORTIUM IS COMPOSED OF 28 PARTNERS

PROJECT COORDINATOR

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UK RESEARCH AND INNOVATION
 UK RESEARCHERS IN MARCO-BOLO ARE SUPPORTED BY THE UKRI HORIZON EUROPE STRENGTHENING
 UNDER THE Grant No. 50564902 (M2), 50563944 (M3) and No. 50564910 (M1C).

00:01:51 00:00:05

MARCO-BOLO
STRENGTHENING BIODIVERSITY OBSERVATION IN SUPPORT OF DECISION MAKING

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[MARCO-BOLO](https://www.linkedin.com/company/marcobolo)

00:01:55 00:00:01

Appendix 10. Project Explainer Infographic

Appendix 11. Press Release

A new EU project has been launched to improve how biodiversity is recorded and protected in marine and coastal environments.

Funded by the Horizon Europe programme, MARCO-BOLO (*MARine Coastal BiODiversity Long-term Observations*) will structure and strengthen European coastal and marine biodiversity observation capabilities, linking them to global efforts to understand and restore ocean health.

Coastal and marine areas are incredibly dynamic and productive oceanic regions, providing significant resources and services for both wildlife and people. They are also subject to intense pressures from agricultural and industry pollution in waterways, dredging, and building development. Many national and regional programmes assess environmental health and human impact on our coasts, but these programmes are often fragmented, short term, and uncoordinated at larger scales.

MARCO-BOLO will address this problem by connecting existing initiatives, optimising and improving methods, and further innovating technologies for biodiversity observations. The project aims to deliver a transformative change in how marine biodiversity is monitored and managed. The research team will engage with diverse stakeholders to tailor research and observation data for direct use, delivering practical tools that will allow politicians and companies to determine biodiversity health, predict changes, monitor changes from imposed policies and proactively manage environments and their biodiversity.

The project has four key objectives:

- Improve acquisition, coordination and delivery of marine, coastal and freshwater biodiversity observations to relevant users.
- Enable technologies for cost-effective, timely and accurate biodiversity observations.
- Test new tools, technologies and models to better understand biodiversity decline.
- Empower European biodiversity observatory operators, data producers and users by creating and sharing best practice guidelines for gathering and using biodiversity data to contribute to biodiversity restoration efforts.

MARCO-BOLO's innovations will address the full pipeline of data collection and use: from testing new monitoring tools using eDNA, robotics, optical and acoustic techniques, to data integration methods for environmental modelling, and guidance on how data can be stored, shared and applied in policy contexts.

Project coordinator Nicolas Pade from [European Marine Biological Resource Centre \(EMBRC\)](#) said:

"We need good data to protect and restore biodiversity effectively. By engaging with policy and decision makers throughout the project, we will ensure that our tools and techniques will support lasting, positive change in how we monitor and protect marine and coastal biodiversity in Europe and internationally."

MARCO-BOLO launched on 1 December 2022 and will run for four years. It is coordinated by the EMBRC and comprises an expert team of 28 partner institutions from 14 countries. For more information, follow [@MARCOBOLO_EU](#).

MARCO-BOLO

STRENGTHENING BIODIVERSITY OBSERVATION IN SUPPORT OF DECISION MAKING

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